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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Estudio de las direcciones de desarrollo del aprendizaje social y emocional en estudiantes de la especialidad de trabajo social

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Resumen

Este artículo examina los niveles de los componentes que aseguran el desarrollo del aprendizaje social y emocional en estudiantes de trabajo social, incluyendo la inteligencia emocional, habilidades sociales y rendimiento académico. El estudio se llevó a cabo entre estudiantes de los cursos II-IV de la Universidad Odlar Yurdu de la República de Azerbaiyán que estudian trabajo social en septiembre de 2023. En el estudio participaron 88 estudiantes de trabajo social. Durante el estudio, se exploraron las posibilidades del aprendizaje social y emocional mediante la medición y aplicación de la inteligencia emocional, habilidades sociales y habilidades de autogestión. La investigación muestra que existe una relación positiva entre el nivel de logro académico y el nivel de habilidades sociales. Esta relación es significativa a un nivel de $p=0.05$ con un bajo nivel de logro académico. La relación entre los logros sociales, el rendimiento académico y la inteligencia emocional es significativa a un nivel de $p=0.001$. Estos hechos demuestran que existe una conexión entre los logros de los componentes del aprendizaje social y emocional y el aumento o disminución de la inteligencia emocional, así como un incremento en los logros académicos, su desarrollo puede sentar las bases para la formación de habilidades sociales.

Palabras clave: aprendizaje social y emocional, inteligencia emocional, habilidades sociales, gestión de las emociones.

Abstract

Study of the directions of development of social and emotional learning in students of the social work specialty

This article examines the levels of components that ensure the development of social and emotional learning in students studying social work, including emotional intelligence, social skills and academic performance. The study was conducted among students of the II-IV courses of the Odlar Yurdu University of the Republic of Azerbaijan studying social work in September 2023. The study involved 88 students studying social work. In the study, the possibilities of social and emotional learning were studied during the measurement and application of emotional intelligence, social skills and self-management skills. Research shows that there is a positive relationship between the level of academic achievement and the level of social skills. This relationship is significant at the level of $p= 0.05$ with a low level of academic achievement. The relationship between social achievements, academic performance and emotional intelligence is

significant at $p = 0.001$. These facts show that there is a link between the achievements of the components of social and emotional learning and the rise or fall of emotional intelligence, as well as an increase in academic achievements, their development can create the basis for the formation of social skills.

Keywords: social and emotional learning, emotional intelligence, social skills, emotion management.

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1. Introduction

Modern era, there is a serious need for the adequate establishment of interpersonal relations in the education system, the raising of educational achievements to the level of the requirements of the time, the formation of empathetic relations to people in an adequate direction, the development of social and emotional learning in order to understand the emotions and feelings of others. As a result of this process, social skills emerge.

Social skills are complex skills and acceptable behaviors that enable people to interact effectively with others and avoid socially inappropriate responses. Social skills are necessary to adapt to different social situations and contribute to a healthy lifestyle (Aghajani et.al., 2014).

Social -emotional learning also lays the foundation for reducing the aggressive behavior of educational subjects, self-awareness of personality and, most importantly, managing emotions. Applying social-emotional learning and educational subjects, especially in social work, which provides professional services to people, enables students to build their work professionally.

Social-emotional learning (SEL) is a strengths-based developmental process that begins at birth and continues throughout life. It's not new, kids It is a process of learning skills to support the healthy development and relationships of children and adults . Social-emotional learning competencies of adults and students include self-awareness , self-management, social awareness, relational skills, and responsible decision-making (Weissberg et al., 2015).

Research shows that social-emotional learning promotes academic achievement, well-being, positive life outcomes, reduces teacher emotional exhaustion, and can be a powerful tool for prevention and resilience when combined with intentionality in curriculum instruction and the school environment (Durlak et al., 2011; Taylor et al., 2017).

It is important to develop a number of competencies during social learning. Research shows that social-emotional learning includes five competencies (Weissberg et al., 2015). They can be grouped as follows:

1. Self-awareness
2. Self-governance.
3. Social awareness.
4. Relationship skills.
5. Responsible decision making (Weissberg et al., 2015).

Social and emotional development affects every area of a child's life. By learning emotional skills from family members, children learn to:

- Recognition of facial expressions.
- Practicing the regulation of emotions.
- Facilitating positive social interactions.

Building social-emotional skills can help a child succeed both academically and in their future careers. They develop problem-solving skills, learn empathy , and become more thoughtful about how they respond to difficult situations. Social-emotional development paves the way for children to respond to different situations as they move through life. For example, positive social- emotional development encourages a child to persevere and keep working to find a solution while maintaining boundaries. Without this foundation, a child may easily give up or resort to negative emotional expressions such as violent behavior when frustrated.

Positive social and emotional development benefits the child as well as their parents, teachers and society. By encouraging young children to develop excellent emotional skills,you help them build better relationships as they grow up (Bavarian, et al.2016).

Research shows that positive social-emotional development also improves mental health, reduces violence in schools, and helps children succeed outside the classroom. Young people begin to understand how to manage their emotions and communicate with others to solve problems, better understand any situation (Bavarian, et al., 2016).

According to various studies, teachers lose eight minutes of time for each lesson to implement disciplinary measures in the classroom . Positive social-emotional development reduces the need for disciplinary measures in schools as the child learns to

express himself and cooperate with teachers and peers. These beneficial effects will then manifest themselves in demands in life, at work, and in personal relationships (Lindsay, 2019).

When you foster positive social and emotional development, you create overall positive child development. This prepares students for better relationships and helps them achieve higher grades in school (Lindsay, 2019). Taking all this into account, we have tried to determine the main directions of social and emotional learning in students studying social work. For this purpose, we aimed to measure emotional intelligence and study the impact of academic achievement on its development in social work requirements. The main point is that social and emotional learning and social skills can be formed by developing the structural components of emotion and intelligence.

2. Literature review

It appears from psychological studies that various contexts of social and emotional learning have been studied (Jabbarov, et.al., 2023; Zins et.al, 2004; Zins & Elias, 2006; Durlak, 2011). Research shows that social-emotional learning refers to the process by which individuals learn and apply a set of social, emotional , and related skills, attitudes , behaviors, and values that help guide students . It also includes the thoughts, feelings, and actions that enable success in school (Ashkanasy & Humphrey, 2011).

Separate studies have noted the relevance of social-emotional learning and emphasize that this issue is necessary and useful for the modern education system. In this regard, Zins et al. (2004) rightly note that teaching and learning in schools have strong social, emotional, and academic components. Students typically do not learn alone but rather in collaboration with their teachers, in the company of their peers, and with the encouragement of their families. (Zins et al., 2004).

Emotions can facilitate or impede children's academic engagement, work ethic, commitment, and ultimate school success. Because relationships and emotional processes affect how and what we learn, schools and families must effectively address these aspects of the educational process for the benefit of all students (Elias et al., 1997).

It should be noted that application in the case of social and learning programs is usually more relevant in childhood and adolescence. Research conducted in this field also proves this. So, SEL programs broadly aim to enhance an interrelated set of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral skills regarded as foundational for academic performance. Skills targeted by SEL programs include the recognition and management of emotions, appreciating others' perspectives, initiating and maintaining positive relationships, and using critical thinking skills to make responsible decisions and handle interpersonal situations (Zins & Elias, 2006). Such competencies promote children's

engagement in instructional activities and the classroom setting that, in turn, enhance academic achievement (Eisenberg, et al. 2010).

Children who successfully develop core social-emotional and behavioral competencies (eg, emotional and behavioral regulation, attention skills) in preschool are more likely to successfully navigate the transition to elementary school (Fantuzzo et al., 2007; Rimm-Kaufman, et.al., 2009). Notably, evidence from longitudinal studies suggests that links between social-emotional skills and academic achievement in early schooling are causal (Raver, 2002). This new knowledge can include both positive and negative behaviors social work practitioners, this theory can be applied to behavioral problems or conflicts.

Social learning theory can also be used to study certain behaviors. Suppose an abusive parent is raising a child. When a child grows up , he may resort to physical violence in his family . In addition, social learning theory can explain other deviant behaviors. For example, a drug addiction can be rationally and socially suppressed by copying the habits of friends, being influenced by others, or simply being surrounded by the “wrong” people (Kolodziej, 2015).

Social learning in education is suitable for teaching multiple students in a classroom because this learning can occur at different levels and in different situations. Children are constantly observing others, making this kind of learning both interactive and continuous. Teachers can support student learning by framing personal experiences as meaningful content, contributing to the community through peer assessment, using group work to develop shared experiences, and expanding the purpose of subject instruction to influence students' personalities (Restad, 2021)

It should be noted that in the academic field, emphasis has been placed on using an integrated approach to promote social and emotional learning due to concerns that multiple unrelated approaches may undermine the validity of any one framework (Tolan et.al. 2016).

Many parallel conceptual frameworks, supported by a solid body of evidence, have emerged independently, and scholars have called for bridging the divide. In this spirit, rather than criticizing the respective strengths of models, school social workers can benefit from exploring different models and finding the one(s) that best fit their school context, students' needs, and strengths (Tolan et.al, 2016).

In fact, for our research, we first need to clarify what constitutes social and emotional learning. What is meant by social and emotional learning? Social-emotional learning is commonly referred to as students' acquisition of skills to recognize and manage emotions, develop empathy and care for others, make responsible decisions, build positive relationships, and deal effectively with difficult life situations (Naimushina, 2019). In this regard, emotional intelligence is no exception.

Identifies five interrelated cognitive, affective and behavioral competencies, which he groups into five main domains of social and emotional skills: social competence ; awareness (understanding your emotions); communication skills; responsible decision-making (Antonia, 2017).

Therefore, social and emotional learning educational technology is more productive in the context of a safe, comfortable learning environment because the key factor in such an environment is a trusting and positive teacher-student relationship that promotes quality learning, social and emotional development, and behavioral competence.

Many studies (Jabbarov et.al, 2023; Kaplánová, 2020; Naimushina, 2019; Kolodziej, 2015), as well as the components reflected in the content of social-emotional learning, bring emotional intelligence to the center of attention. Emotional intelligence is one of the most reliable phenomena to identify and measure social-emotional learning at birth. We believe that in the process of social and emotional learning, a kind of emotional intelligence is developed, which is very important for students studying social work. Because it is more important to manage emotions, build empathy, self-awareness, and develop social skills in their future activities than in other professional fields.

In general, different models of social and emotional learning apply. One of them is a model based on social justice standards. Here, he focuses on impartial, multicultural and socially just education (Teaching Tolerance, 2018). Another model is called the Framework for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL). Here, the framework for social-emotional learning is based on five competencies and attitudes : relationship building, responsible decision-making, self-awareness, self- determination, and social awareness (CASEL, 2021). This framework also applies to emotional intelligence.

In addition, there is a Canadian Model for teaching. This model proposes a six-element model for thriving in learning-focused online environments that is strong enough for all individuals to succeed and have opportunities to experience social-emotional learning skills. The model includes empowering , enhancing, motivating, including, collaborating, and developing employees (Geesa et al., 2022).

Another model is the SAFE (Sequences, Active, Focused, Explicit) model. This model explores measures of safe social-emotional learning (SEL). Here, the consistent development of competences, active forms of learning, competence-focused coping - skills, and the development of attitudes and knowledge are taken into account. (CASEL, 2021).

The American School Counselor Association (ASCA) has developed the Mindsets and Behaviors for Student Success strategy. It focuses on K-12 college and career readiness, standards that describe the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to achieve meaningful academic success, teamwork, and career readiness, and social-emotional

development for every student. Behavioral standards are grouped into three subgroups: learning strategies, self-management skills, and social skills (ASCA, 2021).

The Design Thinking model can also be considered effective for social-emotional learning. Design thinking is a set of creative principles used to explore solutions to problems or solve problems in innovative ways (Brown, 2009).

There are five steps in the design thinking process: 1) Empathize, 2) Define, 3) Brainstorm, 4) Prototype, and 5) Test (Stanford University, 2010). Design thinking includes three distinct elements; design thinking (DT), design thinking process (DTP) and design thinking model (DTM). Geesa et al., 2022).

Among the various approaches, the Online Socio-Emotional Learning model occupies an important place. This model provides opportunities for students and teachers to understand emotions and how to cope with them, support themselves and others, take initiative, build relationships, promote fair treatment, and interact positively with others (Geesa et al., 2022).

A note on social-emotional learning, existing models and research conducted in this area show that the components envisaged in its structure are the main components of emotional intelligence and these components can be measured. From this point of view, emotional intelligence is a person's ability to understand and manage his own emotional experience , as well as the ability to understand the emotions of other people and to be adequate in the emotional situation (Goelman, 2009).

Includes self-regulation, impulsivity control, self-confidence, self-motivation, optimism, communication skills, and the ability to build harmonious relationships with other people (Zvonova, 2018). As you can see, emotional intelligence is a key developable component of social-emotional learning . In this regard, the measurement of emotional intelligence in the study was considered appropriate.

3. Methodology

Design

Is to determine the relationship between social and emotional learning levels and academic achievements and emotional intelligence of social work students. For this purpose, quantitative and qualitative samples were used. The approach used in the study was the example of increasing academic achievement and social skills through the development of emotional intelligence. In addition, we can learn whether communication style can explain the expected relationship between emotional intelligence and social competence within a variable-centered approach. Because students' feeling safe on the

basis of increasing their emotional intelligence can suppress positive behavior for the sake of others and hinder the development of social skills.

Participants

The requirements of students studying social work 22 (14 female students - 8 male) students were taken from each course (I-IV course). A total of 88 students participated in the study. 32 of them were boys (36,35), and 56 (63, 65) were young girls. 95.60% of regularly attending students of both genders participated in classes. Various methods were reported to them and their consent was obtained. After that, the research was carried out.

Instruments

Several methods were used in the research. One of them is Hall's (2007) Emotional Intelligence methodology. N. Hall's method of emotional intelligence facilitates the measurement of emotions, allows to determine the levels of emotional intelligence in different situations of life. The methodology consists of 30 provisions and 5 scales. 1) Emotional awareness - do you understand what emotions you are feeling right now and why you are feeling those emotions? People with high emotional intelligence are more aware of their inner state than others.

2) Ability to control emotions - do you have the ability to control your emotions? Emotions and are you able to use them to achieve certain goals?

3) The ability to control the emotions of others - do you know how to influence other people's feelings?

4) Empathy is the ability to understand and empathize with other people's emotions the emotional state of another person, as well as the desire to provide support. This is the ability to understand a person's situation with facial expressions, gestures, tones of speech, and posture.

5) Self-motivation - the ability to motivate yourself using your own feelings . (Hall, 2007). In addition, 5 types of social skills were taken in the study and their level was determined in the participants.

4. Data collection

The study was conducted among students of the I-IV courses of the Odlar Yurdu University of the Republic of Azerbaijan studying social work in September 2023. The study began with an empirically derived and validated approach to the problem; permission was then sought from the educational institution to access the information through a documentary submission required by the authority. Once agreed, the tools were applied so that the data were entered into SPSS 22 statistical software for differential analysis according to the proposed objectives. After processing, they are clearly presented and summarized in tables with necessary analysis and comments. Data from the questionnaire and methodology were coded and analyzed using the SSPS 22 computer program. We believe that the qualitative analysis of the relationship between

emotional intelligence and academic achievements in these methods determines the development directions of social skills and emotional learning.

Ethical criteria

An ethics committee was involved prior to this study; In addition, the international ethical aspects of beneficence and non-maleficence were taken into account in the study, so the results were aimed at achieving the goals for the benefit of the participants without any intention to harm under any circumstances. Likewise, his physical or mental condition was not impaired (Fouka & Mantzourou, 2011). Since the willingness to participate in the study is subject to informed consent and consent, the principle of autonomy was also taken into account.

5. Results

In order to determine the differences in emotional intelligence between girls and boys with different levels of academic achievement in students studying social work, we divided the sample into 2 groups according to the gender of the respondent, and differences in emotional intelligence were evident in each group. For this, the calculation was made using the Kruskal-Wallis criterion . This was done because the selected sample did not follow a normal distribution. The results are presented in table 1.

Table 1.
Emotional intelligence in various academic achievement requirements indicators

Elements of emotional intelligence	Academic performance lower level	Academic performance average level	Academic performance high level	Criterion H	P-Level
Personal emotions understand	136, 4	260.5	189.8	15.43	0.032
Management of emotions	148.9	234.6	380.5	13.25	0.019
Exponentiation coefficient	183, 2	257, 2	245.5	8.96	0.036
Management of emotions	156.9	330.7	256.4	18.64	0.015
Understanding emotions	144.3	216.9	175.7	12.36	0.074
Intrapersonal EI	168.6	386.5	162.4	14.52	0.086

General of the EU level mourning	1 59.2	326.0	136.3	12.23	0.059
Self-motivation	116.4	242.0	166.8	17.82	0.005
Managing Virgo's emotions	125.8	276.3	148.2	9.96	0.063

Source: compiled by the author

As can be seen from Table 1, the indicators of emotional intelligence at different levels of academic abilities are different. But gender differences did not show themselves. Students with low academic achievement have a low level of understanding their own emotions and the emotions of others . If not otherwise, a high level of emotional intelligence corresponds to a high level of understanding and management of a student's personal emotions. In addition, social skills methodology was used to determine the relationship between academic achievements and emotional intelligence and to determine the levels of social learning. The goal is that students with social skills have high levels of emotional intelligence, and determining its relationship with emotional intelligence will allow to reveal the methodological directions necessary for the development of social and emotional learning. it is possible.

Table 2.
Social skills and academic achievement of social work students relationship indicators

Social skills	Academic achievements	
	Low level	high level
Proper self-presentation skills	-0.118	0.480*
The ability to conduct a conversation correctly	0.216	0.296**
Voice and emotion management skills	-0.128	-486*
Self-presentation skills in the team	0.346	0.274*
Ability to adequately respond to criticism	0.124	0.159
Compliments addressed to a person receptiveness qəbuletmə bacarığı	0.386*	0.098

Note: * k correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-way relationship).

Source: compiled by the author

As can be seen from Table 2, there is a positive relationship between the levels of academic achievement and the level of social skills . This relationship with low level of academic achievement is significant at p=0.05 level. However, there is a connection between the low level of academic achievements and the social skills of students . This relationship is significant at the p=0.05 level. This factor confirms that both levels of academic achievement are related to levels of social skills . But the directions of this

dependence are different. A high level of this dependence is derived from instructional skills , and a low level is related to self-assertion in various areas.

Table 3.
Achievement components of social and emotional learning and academic achievement and emotional intelligence in students

Academic achievements intelligence P of social and emotional learning	Academic achievements	Emotional
Self-confidence 0.001	0.560*	0.430*
Adequate self-assessment 0.000	0.244*	0.256*
Self-management 0.056	0.198	0.380*
Self-defense 0.000	0.358	0.276*
Self-control 0.000	0.289*	0.160

Source: compiled by the author

As can be seen from Table 3, according to the results of the Pearson test, there is a significant relationship between the achievement components of social and emotional learning and academic achievement and emotional intelligence. This relationship is evident in social and emotional learning achievement components and several components of academic achievement and emotional intelligence. However, in some of the social and emotional learning achievement components, this relationship is weak or absent.

As can be seen from Table 3, the relationship between social achievement and academic achievement and emotional intelligence is significant at the level of $r=0.560^*$, $p=0.001$ and $r=0.430^*$, $p=0.001$. As well as. There is a significant relationship between academic achievements and self-confidence and adequate self- –esteem ($r=0.560^*$, $p=0.001$; $r=0.244$, $p=0.000$; $r=0.289$, $p=0.000$). This relationship is the same as between self-confidence and emotional intelligence ($r = .0430$, $p=0.001$), between adequate self-esteem and emotional intelligence ($r= 0.256^*$, $p=0.000$), between self-control and emotional intelligence ($r= 0.380^*$, $p=0.056$), between self-defense and emotional intelligence ($r= 0.276^*$, $p=0.000$) is also observed. These facts show that there is a relationship between the achievement components of social and emotional learning and the rise or fall of emotional intelligence, as well as the increase of academic achievements, their development can create a foundation for the formation of social skills.

It can be assumed that at this time, students go beyond the learning space for self-affirmation because they understand their emotions or because their empathy increases. However, research has shown that there is a significant difference between the achievement components of social and emotional learning and academic achievement, and this is due to the dominance of the majority of components.

As can be seen, there is a significant relationship between the achievement components of social and emotional learning and academic achievement and emotional intelligence. However, these relationships are not significant for all components. This fact confirmed the results of the previous test and it can be concluded that there is a correlative relationship between the social and emotional achievement components of the requirements and their emotional intelligence and academic achievements. From this, it can be concluded that by developing the emotional intelligence of social work students, academic achievements can be increased and most importantly, social skills can be formed. Our proposed approach is justified here. So, the way to increase emotional intelligence is to increase social skills and increase educational achievements.

6. Disccsion

Our research has shown that the relationship between achievement components of social and emotional learning and academic achievement and emotional intelligence is significant. However, this relationship is not universal, with significant correlations corresponding to achievement component substructures of social and emotional learning and some forms of emotional intelligence. Our research is in general agreement with the results of a number of studies. So, Nelson and Low (2003) have related research establishing the relationship of EI skills to academic achievement (Nelson & Low, 2003). Thus, the development of emotional intelligence can have a significant effect on increasing social skills (Jabbarov et al. 2023; Jabbarov, 2017; Behrouz et al., 2008).

Various studies confirm the results of our research. In this regard, it is noted that the development of social skills depends on the development of emotional intelligence. It is social and emotional learning that has a significant impact on expanding and increasing cognitive capabilities (Aghajani et.al., 2014).

A number of studies also emphasize the importance of emotional intelligence in social and emotional learning. Integrity of the emotional mind and the cognitive mind is essential for effective behavior. Negligence of one over the other leads to behavior that is incomplete. EI skills are higher psychological processes which balance the two minds for the achievement of academic success, career and work effectiveness and personal well-being. Emotional illiteracy is reflected in failed marriages, troubled families and social lives. It deteriorates physical health and has its effect in the form of tragedies. The essential skill of EI has to be taught as indispensable similar to traditional measures like IQ. Intrapersonal growth and development is incomplete without having high EI (Basu & Mermillod, 2011). The results of this research show that there is a significant

relationship between emotional intelligence and aggression. Therefore, for the development of social and interpersonal relationships, it is important to develop emotional intelligence and use appropriate training programs covering this area (ehrouz et.al., 2008; Maxwell & Moores, 2008; Robazza et.al., 2004) .

Although a number of studies have indices of conformity according to our study, in others these facts manifest themselves differently. Thus, there are facts that do not confirm the meaningful role of emotional intelligence in the development of social skills. However, the conclusion reached in the studies conducted with students is that for the formation of social skills, it is necessary to develop emotional intelligence and improve academic achievements.

7. Limitations and Further Research

Although the present study is consistent with other studies, there are some limitations. These limitations are primarily due to the inclusion of fewer respondents in the selection process, as well as the inclusion of one university. The data is based on the answers to test questions related to the study of emotional intelligence and academic achievement to implement the social and emotional learning requirements within the university. At the same time, the randomness of the selection and the absence of a solid methodology of social-emotional learning and the diversity of researches in this field complicate the research process . Of course, the data was collected within a limited period of time and was accompanied by a limited number of participants. However, the results obtained in this study can strengthen existing approaches in this field in a specific national-ethnic environment and cultural context and provide different perspectives on scientific circulation with a larger sample size in terms of quantitative analysis for future research.

8. Conclusion

Our study showed that there is a positive relationship between the levels of academic achievement and the level of social skills in social work students. This relationship is significantly associated with lower levels of academic achievement. However, there is a connection between the low level of academic achievements –and the social skills of students. This factor confirms that –both levels of academic achievement are related to levels of social skills . A high level of this dependence is derived from instructional skills , while a low level can be related to self-assertion in various areas.

In the development of social skills, the higher the ability to manage emotions and manage the internal state of the personality, the higher the probability of academic achievements of students.

Research has shown that the development of relationships between emotional intelligence and academic achievement, adequate self-esteem and self-confidence index

during social and emotional learning is a priority in the implementation of this model of learning.

The higher the level of emotional control, the less aggressive reactions to external influences. It was determined that the higher the level of development of intrapersonal emotional intelligence indicators, the lower the level of various negative attitudes towards different people. The higher the ability to understand and manage emotions, the higher the training orientation in the actions of demands. At the same time, the analysis of various studies showed that high indicators of the development of intrapersonal intelligence help students to be less aggressive (Sergienko, 2015) . The higher the level of intrapersonal and interpersonal emotional intelligence, the higher the requirements for empathic responses to others and the foundation for the formation of social skills.

Summing up the research, it can be concluded that social-emotional learning creates the basis for reducing the aggressive behavior of educational subjects, self-awareness of the personality and most importantly, the management of emotions, and this process depends on the level of development of emotional intelligence, as well as the improvement of academic achievements.

Bibliographic References

Aghajani T, Jabbarov R, Mustafayev M. (2014). The effect of playing on children's social skills (Case of study: Preschool children in Tehran) (Persian). **Journal of Iranian Social Development Studies**. 6(3):97-104.

Ashkanasy, NM, & Humphrey, RH (2011). Current Emotion Research in Organizational - Behavior. **Emotion Review**, 3(2), 214-224. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754073910391684>

American School Counselor Association (2021). ASCA Student Standards; Mindsets and Behaviors for Student Success. Alexandria, VA: Author

Anamitra Basu and Martial Mermillod (2011). Emotional Intelligence and Social-Emotional Learning: An Overview. **Psychology Research**, 1, 3, 182-185

Antonia D. (2017) **Emotional intelligence** – Moscow, URL: <https://eikids.ru/-novosti/intervyu-s-davide-antonyatstsa-2.html>

Behrouz, A., Zahra, F., Rezaie, S. & Seied, Z. (2008). The Predictive Effect of Emotional Intelligence and its Components on Anger and Aggressiveness in Soccer Players. **International Journal of Psychology**, 2 (2): 36-51 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271839729_The_Predictive_Effect_of_Emotional_Intelligence_and_its_Components_on_Anger_and_Aggressiveness

Basu A. and Mermillod M. (2011). Emotional Intelligence and Social-Emotional Learning: An Overview. **Psychology Research**, 1:3, 182-185 <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED535684.pdf>

Brown, T. (2009). *Change by Design: How Design Thinking Transforms Organizations and Inspires Innovation*. New York: HarperCollins Publishers.

Bavarian, N., Lewis, KM, Acock, A. et al. (2016). Effects of a School-Based Social-Emotional and Character Development Program on Health Behaviors: A Matched-Pair, Cluster-Randomized Controlled Trial. **J Primary Prevent** 37, 87–105. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10935-016-0417-8>

Durlak, JA, Weissberg, RP, Dymnicki, AB, Taylor, RD, & Schellinger, KB (2011). The Impact of Enhancing Students' Social and Emotional Learning: A Meta-Analysis of School-Based Universal Interventions. **Child Development**, 82, 405-432. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01564.x>

Eisenberg N, Valiente C, Eggum ND (2010). Self-Regulation and School Readiness. *Early Educ Dev.* 1;21(5):681-698. doi: 10.1080/10409289.2010.497451. PMID: 21234283; PMCID: PMC3018834.

Elias, MJ et al. (1997). *Promoting Social and Emotional Learning: Guidelines for Educators*. Alexandria: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development, 163 p. <https://scirp.org/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=2140286>

Fouka, G & Mantzorou, M. (2011). What are the major ethical issues in conducting research? Is there a conflict between the research ethics and the nature of nursing? **Health Science Journal**, 5(1), 3-14

Fantuzzo W, Rebecca Bulotsky-Shearer, Rachel A. Fusco, Christine McWayne (2005). An investigation of preschool classroom behavioral adjustment problems and social-emotional school readiness competencies. **Early Childhood Research Quarterly**, 20:3, 3. 259: 275 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2005.07.00>

Hall, N. (2007). *Positive Psychology and Emotional Intelligence*. Positive Psychology News Daily, NY (Editor SM)

Jabbarov, R., Mustafayev, M., Valiyeva, Y., Babayeva, T., & Abbasova, A. (2023). Study of the relationship between emotional intelligence and aggressiveness in students. *University Notes*, 13 (2), 155–174. <https://doi.org/10.17162/au.v13i2.1440>

Jabbarov R. (2017). Traumatic factors affecting the self-realization of students // **International Journal of Pharmaceutical sciences and research**, 8:6.: 2682-2690. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cites=13519971926371496046&as_sdt=2005&scio dt=0,5&hl=en

Johnson, A., McKay-Jackson, C., & Grumbach, G. (2018). *Critical service-learning toolkit: Social work strategies for promoting healthy youth development*. Oxford University Press.

Kaplanová, A. (2020). Financial awards and their effect on football players' anxiety and coping skills. **Frontiers in Psychology**, 11., 6:3: 13-135

Kolodziej, L. (2015). Model-directed learning. Albert Bandura's social cognitive learning theory and its social-psychological significance for school and instruction. GRIN Verlag.

Lindsay A. Bedna, (2019). Social-Emotional Learning for the Alternative High School Hamline University Saint Paul, Minnesota.

Maxwell, JP, & Moores, E. (2008). Measuring aggressiveness and anger, but not aggression? A response to the CAAS critique. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 9:729–733. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Measuring-aggressiveness-and-anger%2C>

Nelson, D., & Nelson, K. (2003). Emotional intelligence skills: Significant factors in freshman achievement and retention. (ERIC Document Reproduction Service, No. CG032375).

Naimushina LM (2019). Social-emotional learning as a new direction in the development of pedagogical science and practice. **Pedagogy yesterday, today, tomorrow**. 2. 3.41-48.

Payne, AA, & Welch, K. (2015). Restorative justice in schools: The influence of race on restorative discipline. *Youth & Society*, 47 (4), 539–564.

Robazza, C., Pellizzari, M., & Hanin, Y. (2004). Emotion self-regulation and athletic performance: An application of the IZOF model. **Psychology of Sport and Exercise**, 5, 379–404. DOI: 10.1016/S1469-0292(03)00034

Raver, C. (2002). Emotions matter: Making the case for the role of young children's emotional development for early school readiness. *Social Policy Report of the Society for Research in Child Development*, 16, 1-20.

Rimm-Kaufman, SE, Curby, TW, Grimm, KJ, Nathanson, L., & Brock, LL (2009). The contribution of children's self-regulation and classroom quality to children's adaptive behaviors in the kindergarten classroom. **Developmental Psychology**, 45 (4), 958–972. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0015861>

Restad, F. (2021). Exploring the problems and potential of curriculum-making for social learning: Implications for policy and practice. **The Curriculum Journal**.3:5:145-147

Sergienko, EA (2015). The mental model as a new research paradigm of cognitive psychology. *Uchenye zapiski Kazanskogo universiteta. Series: Humanities*. 157(4): 265–279. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/model-psiicheskogo-kak-novaya>

Social Work License Map. (2021, June). Theoretical approaches in social work: Social learning theory. **Retrieved August** 16, 2021, from <https://socialworklicensemap.com/social-work-resources/social-learning-theory-and-its-importance-to-social-work/>

Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning. (2021). The CASEL Guide to Schoolwide SEL Essentials. Retrieved from <https://schoolguide.casel.org/>

Geesa, R. L., Stith, K. M., & Rose, M. A. (2022). Preparing School and District Leaders for Success in Developing and Facilitating Integrative STEM in Higher Education. **Journal of Research on Leadership Education**, 17(2), 139-159. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1942775120962148>

Tolan, P., Ross, K., Arkin, N., Godine, N., & Clark, E. (2016). Toward an integrated approach to positive development: Implications for intervention. **Applied Developmental Science**, 20 (3), 214-236.

Taylor, RD, Oberle E, Durlak JA, Weissberg RP (2017). Promoting Positive Youth Development Through School-Based Social and Emotional Learning Interventions: A Meta-Analysis of Follow-Up Effects. *Child Dev.* 2017 Jul;88(4):1156-1171. doi: 10.1111

Weissberg, RP (2019). Promoting the Social and Emotional Learning of Millions of School Children. **Perspectives on Psychological Science**, 14(1), 65-69. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691618817756>

Zins, JE, & Elias, MJ (2006). Social and emotional learning. In GG Bear & KM Minke (Eds.), **Children's needs III: Development, prevention, and intervention** (pp. 1-13). Bethesda, MD: National Association of School Psychologists.

Zvonova, E.E. (2018). **Education of emotions in the pedagogy** of V. A. Sukhomlinsky. *Psychology of Learning*, 1(3):76-81. <https://moluch.ru/conf/stud/archive/400/16675/> (date of access: 10/17/2022)